

Heating Strategies in Farrowing Compartments: Exploring Configurational Options and the Feasibility of Solar Systems Integration

Kathy Oi In Put^{1,2}, Manon Everaert^{1,2}, Steven Lecompte², Jarissa Maselyne¹

¹*Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), Belgium.*

²*Sustainable Thermo-Fluid Energy Systems, Ghent University (UGent), Belgium.*

Kathy.Put@ilvo.vlaanderen.be

Abstract

Maintaining ideal climate conditions in the farrowing compartment presents a complex and energy-intensive challenge in pig husbandry due to the conflicting thermoneutral zones of sows (19-22°C) and piglets (29-35°C) (Hörtenhuber et al., 2020), requiring a tailored microclimate for piglets. The study focuses on optimizing various heating strategies within farrowing compartments and evaluating the feasibility of transitioning to renewable energy. Initially, three heating configurations were tested at Varkenscampus in Melle, Belgium. These scenarios comprised manually controlled heat lamps and underfloor heating (S1), solely automatic heat lamps (S2), and automatic heat lamps with coverings (S3). Temperature sensors in the pens collected environmental data, while energy usage was monitored to calculate costs. Results indicate that S3 effectively creates a localized heat environment, reducing heat loss and electricity use by 30% compared to S2 and 25% compared to S1. However, further investigation is warranted to assess its performance in colder weather. Subsequently, solar energy and heat pump feasibility for the farrowing compartment was evaluated using DesignBuilder simulations. Scenarios (S1, S2, S3) were simulated alongside variations such as natural gas floor heating (S1) and a heat pump (S1HP). Results suggest that while S3 is the most cost-effective, S1HP is the most ecologically beneficial. Nevertheless, neither S1HP nor S3, combined with batteries, yielded positive Net Present Values over a 10-year period. Hence, a combined approach with other renewable systems is advised for sustainable electricity supply. These findings underscore the importance of different heating configurations for piglets in the farrowing compartment, as well as the challenges of integrating renewable energy sources for long-term viability and economic feasibility.

Keywords: thermoneutral zone, heating strategies, pigs, solar system, heat pump

Introduction

Agriculture's energy consumption impacts food production and sustainability, contributing 21-37% of global greenhouse gas emissions (Mbow, 2019). According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), livestock farming accounts for 7.6% of greenhouse gas emissions, attributed to the direct energy consumption of animal farms (Costantino et al., 2023). Pig farming, known for high energy use, shows varied consumption, ranging from 18 kWh to 45 kWh per pig produced (Teagasc, 2020). Ventilation and heating constitute a significant portion of energy usage in farming operations. In breeding farms, ventilation and heat lamps contribute to 50% and 17% of total electricity usage, respectively. In fattening farms, ventilation accounts for 75% of energy consumption. (Enerpedia, 2023). Efficient heating strategies are crucial for energy and economic benefits.

The thermoneutral zone (TNZ) defines the temperature range where animals maintain stable body temperature without extra energy expenditure (Yousef, 1985). In pig farming, the TNZ depends on the age of the pig and the housing condition. Typically, 10°C to 26°C is defined as the TNZ for sows (Hill et al., 2020; Malmkvist et al., 2012). High temperatures (>25°C) can reduce feed intake and milk yield (Bjerg et al., 2020), and increase the risk of piglet crushing (Xin, 1999). The optimal temperature range in the first two weeks is 29°C to 35°C (Hörtenhuber et al., 2020). Additionally, cold stress can contribute to neonatal morbidity and mortality in piglets (Carroll et al., 2012). Distinct temperature needs highlight the necessity for separate heating methods: ambient for sows and localized for piglets in farrowing compartments. Common heating methods for piglets in the swine industry include heat lamps, electric mats, floor heating, and covered zones. Combining heat lamps with floor heating provides effective localized warmth, with floor heating offering uniform warmth, akin to maternal warmth, and heat lamps offering concentrated warmth. While retrofitting older buildings with underfloor heating can be costly, automatic heat lamps with coverings promise to reduce energy consumption by 90% (*VENG heating lamps*, n.d.). However, further research is needed to assess energy use and heat efficiency. Different configurations of this system also warrant investigation for optimal performance.

In addition, the livestock industry is embracing renewable energy solutions like solar panels and anaerobic digesters to cut down on environmental impact and lessen dependence on non-renewable resources (Csatári, 2014). However, more research and investment are needed to fully integrate and optimize these technologies across diverse farming settings.

The research presented here contains two parts: (1) comparing heating configurations for financial benefits while maintaining pig comfort, and (2) exploring the feasibility of transitioning to a solar thermal system and heat pump alongside the optimal heating configuration.

1. Heating configuration options

Three heating configurations were tested in a pig barn at the "Varkenscampus" in Melle, Belgium. The current system in the farrowing compartments includes underfloor heating (40°C water) supplemented by manually controlled heat lamps. The ventilation system serves dual purposes: air purification through minimal ventilation and temperature control via adjustable rates based on room temperature. Two other heating configurations using automatic heat lamps with and without covering were tested. All configurations were compared in terms of local temperature conditions and energy usage.

1.1 Methodology

The experimental setup of the three scenarios is as follows (Figure 1):

- Scenario 1 (S1): Underfloor heating & manually controlled heat lamp (ON, reduced power, OFF)
- Scenario 2 (S2): Solely automatic heat lamp (Automatic power adjustment from 0 to 100%)
- Scenario 3 (S3): Automatic heat lamp & covering

Figure 1. Experimental set-up of the three heating configurations.

Figure 2. Plan of the farrowing compartment and the experimental placement.

S1 acts as the control condition, including underfloor heating and a manually controlled heat lamp, representing the conventional heating method. S2 and S3 replace the manually controlled heat lamps with the automatic ones, eliminating underfloor heating to simulate conditions in farming buildings without floor heating. All three scenarios were tested simultaneously on two farrowing pens each in the same compartment (Figure 2), with half of the compartment's floor heating system deactivated for S2 and S3. Temperature sensors collected data on room temperature (T_R) and local ambient temperature (T_A) in vicinity of the sows and piglets. Energy plugs and flow rate meters were used to measure the energy use of heating devices. Other variables like sow weight and piglet numbers were beyond experimental control.

The experiment was executed for one farrowing cycle, with sows introduced one week before farrowing. Heat lamps were activated 2-3 days pre-delivery. On the delivery day (day 0), the manually controlled heat lamps ran at reduced power (S1), while the automatic heat lamps were switched to automatic mode (S2 & S3). Manual lamps were turned off 3-4 days post-birth, while the automatic ones remained operational until day 14. S1 initiates underfloor heating upon sow entry, while S2 and S3 lack it throughout the cycle. Sows and piglets stay in the compartment for four weeks post-birth, completing the cycle.

1.2 Results and Discussion

Comfort conditions

The T_A near the sows fluctuate between 23°C and 30°C in line with outside temperature trends (Figure 3(a)). S1 and S3 show similar patterns, while S2 exhibits relatively lower temperatures. Notably, a ventilation system breakdown before farrowing and a heatwave from September 4th to 11th potentially influenced outcomes. In Figure 3(b), the piglets' T_A ranges from 25°C to 30°C, with S2 displaying larger fluctuations due to the automatic behaviour of the heat lamp.

Figure 3. Overview of sows (a) and piglets' (b) ambient temperature of the three scenarios.

Figure 4. Density distribution graph of sows (a) & piglets' (b) measured T_A . (Yellow highlighted area: Sows' TNZ, Red highlighted area: Piglets' TNZ)

For the three scenarios, the density distribution of measured temperatures for both piglets and sows are observed (Figure 4). In Figure 4(a), S1 and S2 curves for sows exhibit multiple peaks, indicating a high variation in measured temperatures, while S3 shows a unimodal curve. Notably, temperatures in S1 and S3 mostly exceed the TNZ for sows. In Figure 4(b), all piglet scenarios show a unimodal distribution, with S3 peaking within the TNZ, indicating effective heat provision.

S1, the baseline for compartment heating, uses underfloor heating to maintain a constant T_A of the piglets. However, sows' T_A often increase with elevated piglets' T_A . By comparing the temperature curve of sows and piglets across the three scenarios, the results show that S3 creates a favourable piglet microclimate without significantly affecting the T_A of sows, achieved through coverings establishing a consistent environment. S2, relying solely on automatic heat lamps, maintains lower piglet T_A than S1 & S3 and faces challenges in achieving the TNZ.

Energy use

Electricity usage during the experiment primarily comes from operating heat lamps and the ventilation system. In this work, the main focus lies on the operation of the heat lamps as the ventilation could not be measured separately for the farrowing compartment. Heat lamps in S1 were manually operated, consuming about 175W at full power and 100W at reduced power. In S2 & S3, automatic heat lamps started at 150W for the first two days and then adjusted power based on piglets' T_A . The cumulative energy use from heat lamps is depicted in Figure 5, with a data gap for S2 and S3 due to a Wi-Fi outage lasting at least 4-5 days. The heat exchange rate of S1 underfloor heating fluctuates between 100W and 150W, and the total energy used from underfloor heating for S1 in one pen over the 5-week period amounts to 65.074 kWh.

Figure 5. Energy use of heat lamps and underfloor heating in kWh over the farrowing period.

Using the energy consumption data (Figure 5) and Belgium's electricity prices (*Electricity and gas prices stabilise in 2023*, 2023), an economic analysis was done. Electricity and gas prices in the first half of 2023 were 0.3592 €/kWh and 0.1043 €/kWh, respectively. S2 exhibits higher energy use (Table 1) due to significant heat losses as compared to a covered or underfloor heating scenario. Despite both S2 & S3 relying solely on electricity, S2 incurs the highest costs, while S3 emerges as the most cost-effective option, being approximately 30% cheaper than S2 and about 25% more cost-effective than S1. It's noteworthy that the research was conducted during summer, coinciding with a heatwave, leading to a reduced heating load. The cost assessment did not take into account ventilation.

Table 1. Energy consumption and energy prices across different scenarios over a 5-week cycle.

Scenario	Electricity (kWh)	Gas (kWh)	Total energy cost for one pen (€)	Total energy cost for one compartment (€)	
S1	S1-1	20.21	65.07	14.05	224.80
	S1-2	18.42	65.07	13.41	214.56
S2	S2-1	42.61	-	15.30	244.80
	S2-2	44.88	-	16.12	257.92
S3	S3-1	31.15	-	11.19	179.04
	S3-2	27.23	-	9.78	156.48

2. Heat Pump, solar energy & electricity storage system integration

The goal of this part is to investigate renewable energy solutions for the electricity and heating of the farrowing barn, using the various heating scenarios tested before. A business model will assess the feasibility of transitioning to a heat pump (for S1), solar & electricity storage system for the optimal scenarios.

2.1 Methodology

DesignBuilder (DesignBuilder Software Ltd., Stroud, United Kingdom) simulated yearly temperature and energy consumption profiles using experiment data, occupancy details, and electricity usage patterns as inputs. External factors such as weather, building materials, and location specifics (latitude 50.99, longitude 3.78) were considered. The three scenarios (S1, S2, S3) were simulated, with S1 further optimized by replacing the gas boiler with an electric heat pump (S1HP). The ventilation system for all scenarios was Constant Air Volume (CAV), while heating, ventilating, and air-conditioning (HVAC) systems varied:

- S1: CAV system, underfloor heating with gas boiler
- S1HP: CAV system, underfloor heating with electric heat pump
- S2: CAV system, automatic heat lamp
- S3: CAV system, automatic heat lamp (70% power output)

S3 incorporated a 70% power output automatic heat lamp based on experimental results compared to S2.

Additionally, a Photovoltaic Thermal (PVT) system was utilized for S1 and a Photovoltaic (PV) system for S1HP, S2, and S3, situated on the south-east-oriented roof. Subsequently, scenarios integrating PV/PVT systems were evaluated based on the required panel numbers, annual production, and residual grid electricity/gas needs, to determine the optimal scenarios. This involved calculating solar capacity installation based on annual electricity consumption, followed by calculating yearly production and remaining grid electricity requirements. Optimal scenarios were then selected for further refinement, integrating PV/PVT with electricity/thermal storage systems for nighttime usage. Python calculations determined the optimal number of panels and battery sizes for the selected scenarios, considering varying numbers of panels and different battery sizes relative to energy cost. Surplus energy was stored in the battery with a 90% Depth of Discharge (DoD), and discharged when electricity would be taken from the grid. Remaining grid energy needs are multiplied by the electricity cost (0.3592€/kWh) for the final total energy cost (*Electricity and gas prices stabilise in 2023, 2023*). Net Present Value (NPV) analysis considers CAPEX, OPEX, self-consumption savings, and potential revenue from excess electricity sales over a 10-year period.

2.2 Results and Discussion

PV/PVT panel to cover the yearly consumption of each scenario are shown in Table 2. While the total annual production meets the total annual demand, hourly production falls short at night, especially in winter, necessitating significant grid usage. S3 demonstrates the least grid dependence after solar integration. Among underfloor heating scenarios, S1HP relies exclusively on electricity, rendering it potentially more ecological than S1. Thus, S1HP and S3 are selected for further optimization by integrating a PV & electricity storage system to enhance self-consumption and reduce grid reliance.

Table 2. Yearly consumption, solar production and demand from the grid after PVT (for S1) & PV (for S1HP, S2 and S3) integration across the scenarios.

	S1	S1HP	S2	S3
No. of PV/PVT panels ($350W_p$) (panels)	28	45	34	23
Yearly production (kWh)	12026	19843	14864	9763
Electricity from the grid (kWh)	8064	13031	9707	6265
Gas from the grid (kWh)	28727	-	-	-

By further optimization with the PV & electricity storage system, results show that cost reduction is significant with up to 25 panels for S1HP and 15 panels for S3. Results show a 25-kWh battery yields the highest NPV (-16,832 €) for S1HP, while a 17-kWh battery yields the highest NPV (-5,467 €) for S3.

Figure 6. State of charge (SoC) of 25-kWh (S1HP) (a) & 17-kWh (S3) (b) battery and grid demand after the storage system.

Figure 6 shows that with S1HP (25 panels, 25-kWh battery) and S3 (15 panels, 17-kWh battery), the batteries quickly discharge due to high night-time electricity demand, resulting in insufficient stored electricity for night-time or winter use. Despite consuming up to 70% of generated electricity (self-consumption), grid electricity only slightly decreased from 1,303 MWh to 1,103 MWh for S1HP and from 626 MWh to 473 MWh for S3. In light of these findings, a 100% transition to renewables with only a PV and battery system and without the electricity grid for S1HP and S3 is not feasible.

Conclusions and future work

Among the three heating strategies tested in a farrowing compartment, automatic heat lamps with a cover (S3) appear promising for providing localized piglet heating while minimizing

sow impact. However, an experiment during winter is necessary to confirm if there is adequate heating without underfloor heating. During this test, S3 had circa 25% less estimated energy costs than manual heat lamps with underfloor heating (S1). Both S1 and S3 offer energy-efficient options, with S3 particularly suitable for buildings where installing underfloor heating is challenging. Simulation models indicate that integrating PV panels and an electric heat pump is most favourable for S1, while PV panels alone are a viable renewable energy solution for S3. However, achieving a 100% transition to renewables without connection to the electricity grid poses challenges to be cost-effective. Future research should expand the experimental scope to include diverse heating configurations or locations, aiming to enhance the database for improved design of sustainable heating solutions for pig farming.

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